

TO FORMULATE & EVALUATE HERBAL CRACK CREAM FOR HEALING & MOISTURIZING CRACKED SKIN

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ABSTRACT

Feet play a vital role in daily activities such as walking, running, and jumping, but they are frequently overlooked in personal care. Maintaining foot health is important to prevent conditions like cracked heels. The present study focused on the preparation and development of a herbal anti-crack gel formulated with aloe vera gel and centella extract, turmeric extract which possess wound-healing and antimicrobial properties. Ingredients known for their anti-inflammatory effects were also included in the formulation. Microbial evaluation was performed to assess the gel's effectiveness. The formulated cream was observed to be safe and beneficial in reducing cracked heels without producing adverse effects. The primary purpose of this cream is to moisturize and nourish cracked heels. Such cream a protective oily layer on the skin surface, which helps minimize moisture loss and Keeps the skin hydrated. Water in the formulation provides a cooling and

refreshing effect. Essential oil is incorporated to provide a pleasant fragrance. The prepared cream showed good homogeneity, smooth spreadability, and a naturally greasy texture characteristic.

KEYWORDS: Herbal Anti-Crack Cream, Aloevera Gel, Centella Extract, Turmeric Extract, Cold Cream, Antimicrobial Activity, Anti-Inflammatory Agents, Foot Care, Moisturizing Cream, Essential Oil.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are substances used to enhance or improve physical appearance. The term “cosmetic” is derived from the greek word “kosmetikos” which means beautifying or adorning.^[1] the skin is the largest organ of the human body, covering nearly 20 square feet. It mainly consists of three layers, among which the epidermis is the outermost layer that acts as a protective waterproof barrier and contributes to skin colour.^[2] Skin also serves as the body’s primary defence against external environmental factors.^[3]

The feet are one of the most important parts of the body and are continuously exposed to pressure, friction, and environmental stress. Unlike many other body parts, the sole of the foot does not contain sebaceous (oil) glands, making it more prone to dryness and cracking.^[4] the forefoot region contains five metatarsal bones that connect the toes to the rest of the foot. Excessive pressure on these bones may lead to pain, commonly known as metatarsalgia.^[5]

The skin present on the feet is classified as thick skin and is composed of five layers: stratum basale, stratum spinosum, stratum granulosum, stratum lucidum, and stratum corneum. Due to the absence of oil glands, the skin of the feet often becomes dry, rough, and painful. Heel fissures or cracked heels are common conditions resulting from excessive dryness. Conventional synthetic creams used for treating cracked heels may sometimes cause irritation, redness, burning, or stinging sensations.^[6]

Herbal heel fissure creams are prepared using natural ingredients and are considered safer for regular use because they contain fewer artificial chemicals. Ingredients such as aloe vera are widely used in herbal formulations because of their moisturizing, soothing, and skin-healing properties. Aloe vera contains several bioactive compounds that help nourish and protect the skin without causing significant harmful effects.^[7]

An herbal crack cream is a topical formulation developed using natural plant-based ingredients that possess moisturizing, keratolytic, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties. The formulation of herbal crack cream focuses on deep skin nourishment, regeneration of damaged tissues, and prevention of microbial infection. Herbal ingredients such as aloe vera, turmeric, coconut oil and gotu kola are commonly incorporated because of their excellent moisturizing, anti- inflammatory, and collagen-stimulating properties. These ingredients help soften the hard skin layer, improve elasticity, and accelerate the healing process of fissured heels.^[8]

The skin acts as the body's outermost barrier and often reflects the earliest signs of ageing. Today, early skin ageing has become a growing issue worldwide, mainly due to environmental pollution and changing lifestyles. Feet play a vital role in supporting body movement and are regularly exposed to continuous pressure and friction. Unlike other parts of the body, the skin on the feet has minimal oil secretion, making it more susceptible to excessive dryness, rough texture, and cracking.^[9]

The herbal foot cream is developed using naturally derived ingredients aloe vera, neem, turmeric, coconut oil and gotu kola. Gotu kola is widely recognized for its ability to promote collagen synthesis and repair damaged skin hydration, whereas neem extract contributes antimicrobial and antifungal benefits. Aloe vera provides soothing hydration to the skin, while lemongrass oil offers a pleasant natural aroma. Herbal ingredients are generally preferred over synthetic chemicals because they are cost-effective, readily accessible, and less likely to produce adverse effects. In addition, vitamin e, which has anti-inflammatory and skin-protective properties that may help repair and reduce cracks resulting from skin dryness.^[10]

Topical creams are among the most widely used semisolid dosage forms in cosmetic and dermal care because they can deliver both lipophilic and hydrophilic ingredients in a convenient, elegant, and consumer-acceptable form. Oil-in-water creams are especially preferred when a non-greasy feel, easy washability, and rapid skin spread are desired.^[11]

1.1 What are cracks?

Cracks, also known as fissures, are splits or openings that develop on the skin due to excessive dryness. When the skin loses moisture, it becomes rough, hard, and less flexible, which can eventually lead to the formation of deep lines or breaks, especially around the heels. In severe cases, these fissures may become painful and uncomfortable.^[12] daily habits, environmental conditions, and improper foot care can contribute to the development of cracked skin, so regular observation of routine activities and skin condition is important for prevention.^[13]

Fig. No. 01: crack heel.^[14]

- **Reason of cracking**

Cracking of the heels mainly occurs due to inadequate moisture in the skin. When the skin on the feet becomes excessively dry and rough, it loses elasticity and eventually develops fissures or cracks.

- **Deficiencies**

Heel cracks can develop due to several factors, including poor nutrition and insufficient intake of important nutrients such as zinc, vitamins, and minerals, which are necessary for maintaining healthy skin.

- **Pressure:** prolonged standing at home or at work can cause tension in the 16.

- **Ageing skin**

Ageing also contributes, as the skin gradually becomes dry, thick, and less flexible over time. In addition, certain health conditions like diabetes, eczema, psoriasis, thyroid disorders, and fungal infections such as athlete's foot may increase the likelihood of cracked heels.^[15,16]

- ❖ **Dry soles**

Dry soles of the feet refer to a condition where the skin on the bottom (plantar surface) of the feet becomes rough, flaky, scaly, or cracked due to a loss of moisture and natural oils. The dryness may be mild, causing a slightly rough texture, or severe, resulting in deep fissures, pain, and possible secondary infections.

- ❖ **Commonly affected areas**

- I. Ball of the foot
- II. Lateral edges of the sole.
- III. Heels^[17]

1.2 Advantages

- ❖ Moisturizes skin, soothing effect, promotes wound healing.
- ❖ Helps repair cracked heels & damaged skin by supporting tissue regeneration & collagen formation.
- ❖ Provides hydration and reduces dryness, roughness, and scaling of the skin.
- ❖ Herbal ingredients help reduce redness, irritation, pain, and inflammation.

1.3 Disadvantages

- ❖ The effectiveness can vary depending on the quality and source of herbal ingredients.
- ❖ Some people may develop irritation, redness, itching, or sensitivity to herbal extracts.
- ❖ Some herbal active compounds may not penetrate deeply into thick cracked skin.
- ❖ Repeated application is often required for effective healing.

2. Drug profile

Api (drug)

- ❖ centella extract

Table No. 1 Pharmacognostic and therapeutic profile of centella extract used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.^[18]

Parameter	Details
Name of extract	Centella extract
Botanical name	Centella asiatica
Family	Apiaceae
Biological source	Centella asiatica consists of the dried whole plant of centella asiatica (L.) Urban
Active constituents	Asiaticoside, madecassoside, asiatic acid, madecassic acid
Therapeutic uses	Wound healing ,crack heel treatment ,skin repair and Moisturizing
Mechanism of Action	Stimulates collagen synthesis ,promotes wound healing and tissue repair

Fig. No. 02 :- Centella Extract.

❖ **Turmeric Extract**

Table no. 2:- Pharmacognostic and Therapeutic profile of turmeric (*curcuma longa*) used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.^[19,20]

Parameter details	Details
Name of extract	Turmeric extract
Botanical name	<i>Curcuma longa</i>
Family	Zingiberaceae
Biological source	Dried rhizome (underground stem) of <i>curcuma longa</i>
Active constituents	Curcuminoids (primarily curcumin)
Therapeutic uses	Anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant
Mechanism of action	Inhibits inflammatory pathways, scavenges free radicals, suppresses Microbial growth

Fig. No. 03: Turmeric extract.

❖ **Aloevera**

Table no. 3: Pharmacognostic and Therapeutic Profile of Aloevera used in Herbal Crack Cream formulation.^[21]

Parameter	Details
Name of extract	Aloevera
Botanical name	Aloevera
Family	Asphodelaceae
Biological source	The medicinal aloe gel is obtained from the fleshy leaves of the plant.
Active constituents	Anthraquinones, polysaccharides, vitamins
Therapeutic uses	Treatment of minor cuts and irritation, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial applications
Mechanism of Action	Stimulates fibroblast activity and collagen formation

Fig. No. 04: Alovera.

Excipients

❖ Almond Oil

Table No. 4: Following Emollient used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Prunus amygdalus oil
Common name	Almond oil
Category	Emollient
Appearance	Pale yellow liquid
Nature	Natural fixed oil functions in formulation Used to nourish and soften skin

Fig. No. 05: Almond Oil.

❖ Coconut Oil

Table no. 5: Following Emollient used in herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Cocos nucifera oil
Common name	Coconut oil
Category	Moisturizing agent
Appearance	Clear to white semi solid
Nature	Natural oil functions in formulation used To prevent dryness and moisture loss

Fig. No. 06: Coconut Oil.

❖ Emulsifying Wax

Table No. 6: Following Emulsifying Agent used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Emulsifying wax
Common name	E-wax
Category	Emulsifying agent
Appearance	White waxy solid
Nature	Non-ionic wax functions in formulation Used to stabilize oil and water phases

Fig. No. 07: Emulsifying Wax.

❖ Cetyl Alcohol

Table No. 7: Following Thickening Agent used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Cetyl alcohol
Common name	Palmityl alcohol
Category	Thickening agent
Appearance	White waxy flakes
Nature	Fatty alcohol functions in formulation Used to improve consistency and texture

Fig. No. 08: Cetyl Alcohol.

❖ Stearic Acid

Table No. 8: Following Stiffening Agent Used In Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Stearic acid
Common name	E-wax
Category	Emulsifying agent
Appearance	White waxy solid
Nature	Non-ionic wax functions in formulation Used to stabilize oil and water phases

Fig. No. 09: Stearic Acid.

❖ **Vitamin E**

Table no. 9: Following Antioxidant Used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation Parameter.

Chemical name	Tocopherol
Common name	Vitamin e
Category	Antioxidant
Appearance	Yellow viscous liquid
Nature	Fat soluble vitamin functions in formulation used To protect skin and prevent oxidation

Fig. No. 10:- Vitamin E.

❖ **Glycerine**

Table no. 10: Following Humectant Used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Glycerol
Common name	Glycerine
Category	Humectant
Appearance	Clear viscous liquid
Nature	Polyol compound functions in formulation Used to retain moisture in skin

Fig. No. 11: Glycerin.

❖ Propylene Glycol

Table No. 11: Following Co-Solvent Used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Propylene glycol
Common name	Pg
Category	Co-solvent
Appearance	Clear colorless liquid
Nature	Synthetic compound functions in formulation used to enhance penetration and moisturization

Fig. No. 12: Propylene Glycol.

❖ Peppermint Oil

Table no. 12: Following Cooling Agent Used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Mentha piperita oil
Common name	Peppermint oil
Category	Cooling / flavoring agent
Appearance	Clear volatile liquid
Nature	Essential oil functions in formulation Used to provide cooling effect and pleasant odour

Fig. No. 13: Peppermint Oil.

❖ Methyl Paraben

Table no. 13 :- Following Preservative Used in Herbal Crack Cream Formulation.

Chemical name	Methyl parahydroxybenzoate
Common name	Methyl paraben
Chemical formula	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃
Category	Preservative
Appearance	White crystalline powder
Odour	Odourless or faint characteristic odour

Fig. No. 14: Methyl Paraben.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Extraction Method

1. Preparation of Aloe Extract

1. Fresh and healthy aloe vera leaves were collected from the two year old plant of about 50 to 60 cm in length.
2. The collected leaves were then washed with the distilled water and dried in the hot air oven.
3. After complete drying the outer part of aloe vera leaf was removed longitudinally using a sterile knife.
4. Afterwards the colourless parenchymatous tissue (aloe vera gel) was removed by sterile knife.
5. Then fibres and impurities were removed by filtration by using muslin cloth and filtrate or filter product which is clear aloe vera gel was used in the formulation.^[22]

2. Preparation of Centella Extract

1. Fresh leaves of centella asiatica were collected and washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove dirt and impurities. The leaves were shade dried for 7–10 days until complete drying.
2. Dried leaves were powdered using a grinder to obtain coarse powder.
3. The powdered material was soaked in ethanol or distilled water for 24–48 hours for extraction.
4. The mixture was filtered using muslin cloth or filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated by evaporating the solvent at low temperature.
5. The obtained extract was dried and stored in an airtight container for further use in formulation.^[23]

3. Preparation of Turmeric Extract

1. Fresh rhizomes of turmeric were collected and washed.
2. Rhizomes were sliced into small pieces. The pieces were shade dried completely.
3. Dried material was ground into fine powder. Powder was stored in an airtight container.^[24]

4. Formulation of Herbal Crack Cream

Step 1: Preparation of Oil Phase

oil phase ingredients such as emulsifying wax, stearic acid, almond oil, cetyl alcohol, peppermint oil, coconut oil were weighed and heated in the beaker at temperature 60- 70 c to form liquid.

Fig. No. 15: Oil Phase.

Step 2:- Preparation of Water Phase

water phase ingredients distilled water, glycerine, propylene glycol and methyl paraben were weighed and heated with continuous stirring in beaker at temperature of 60-70^{0c} until it forms liquid.

Fig. No. 16: Water Phase

Step 3: Emulsification

Slowly add the hot water phase into the oil phase with continuous stirring. Stir continuously until a uniform cream is formed.

Step 4: Coolings

Allow the cream to cool gradually While Stirring continuously. When Temperature becomes around 40°C, add: turmeric extract, aloe vera extract, centella extract, vitamin e, Preservative

Fig. No. 17: Formulation of Herbal Crack Cream [f1 to f8 batch].

❖ **Formula of herbal crack cream [f1 to f5].**

Sr.No	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Centella extract	0.40g	0.45g	0.35g	0.40g	0.42g	0.38g	0.40g	0.45g
2	Turmeric extract	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g	0.12g	0.10g	0.10g	0.12g	0.10g
3	Aloe vera gel	1.00g	1.00g	1.20g	1.00g	1.10g	1.00g	1.00g	1.10g
4	Almond oil	1.00ml	1.20ml	0.80 ml	1.00ml	1.10ml	0.90ml	1.00ml	1.15ml
5	Coconut oil	0.50ml	0.60ml	0.40 ml	0.50ml	0.55ml	0.45ml	0.50ml	0.60ml
6	Emulsifying wax	1.10g	1.20g	1.00g	1.30g	1.15g	1.05g	1.25g	1.20g
7	Cetyl alcohol	0.35g	0.40g	0.30g	0.45g	0.38g	0.32g	0.42g	0.40g
8	Stearic acid	0.40g	0.45g	0.35g	0.50g	0.42g	0.38g	0.48g	0.45g
9	Vite	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g	0.10g
10	Distilled water	12.3ml	11.8 ml	12.8 ml	11.6ml	12.03ml	12.53ml	11.83ml	11.78ml
11	Glycerin	1.50ml	1.60ml	1.40ml	1.50ml	1.55ml	1.45ml	1.60ml	1.50ml
12	Propylene Glycol	0.50ml	0.50ml	0.50ml	0.50ml	0.50ml	0.50ml	0.50ml	0.50ml
13	Peppermint oil	0.03ml	0.03ml	0.03ml	0.03ml	0.03ml	0.03ml	0.03ml	0.03ml
14	Methyl paraben	0.04g	0.04g	0.04g	0.04g	0.04g	0.04g	0.04g	0.04g
	Total	20g	20g	20g	20g	20g	20g	20g	20g

5. Evaluation of herbal crack cream**5.1 Physical Examination^[26]**

The appearance of the cream was determined by its colour, its texture and its odour.

5.2 Skin Irritation Test

The prepared cream was applied to the desired area of skin. After an hour, the skin was checked for any irritation, redness, or swelling.

5.3 Washability Test

Small amount of the prepared cream was applied evenly to a specific area of the skin and then exposed to running water for a certain period of time. After that, it was observed how

easily the cream washed off from the skin surface, and the results were recorded.

5.4 Ph Determination

Solution of the cream was prepared by weighing 1 g of cream and dissolving it in 10 ml of water. Once the proper solution was prepared, the ph value was determined using ph paper.^[27,28,29]

5.5 Viscosity Test^[30]

The viscosity of the formulated batches was determined using brookfield viscometer with spindle of 64 at 20 rpm. The formulation whose viscosity was determined was added to a beaker. The spindle was allowed to move freshly into crack cream and reading was noted.

5.6 Spreadability^[29]

A small amount of cream is placed between two slides .a weight is applied and the time taken for the upper slide to move is noted.

5.7 Stability Test

The cream is stored at refrigerator temperature and room temperature for a specific period and for any changes.

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

❖ Table No. 14: Physical Examination

- The appearance of the cream was determined by its colour, its texture and its odour.
- F7 batch was selected the optimized formulation due to its excellent homogeneity, soft elegant texture and acceptable appearance.
- It showed superior physical properties and better stability compared to other formulation.

Sr. No	Formulations	Colour	Odour	Homogeneity	Texture	Result
1.	F1	Off White	Mild herbal	Non - uniform	Rough	Poor
2.	F2	Milky White	Charateristics	Good	Soft	Good
3.	F3	Pale White	Mild Turmeric	Good	Uniform	Good
4.	F4	White	Pleasant	Excellent	Fine	Good
5.	F5	Creamish White	Slight oily	Good	Slightly Greasy	Good
6.	F6	Glossy white	Pleasant	Excellent	Smooth	Good
7.	F7	Pearl	Charateristics	Excellent	Soft,	Excellent

		White			Elegance	
8.	F8	Light white	Cream odour	Good	Smooth	Good

❖ **Table no. 15: Skin Irritation Test**

- The prepared cream was applied to the desired area of skin. After an hour, the skin was checked for any irritation, redness, or swelling.
- The f7 formulation showed no signs of skin irritation such as redness, itching, or inflammation during the skin irritation test. Hence, f7 was considered the optimized and best batch, indicating that the herbal crack cream is safe and suitable for topical application on the skin.

Sr. No	Formulation	Observation	Result
1.	F1	No irritation	Pass
2.	F2	No irritation	Pass
3.	F3	No irritation	Pass
4.	F4	No irritation	Pass
5.	F5	No irritation	Pass
6.	F6	No irritation	Pass
7.	F7	No irritation	Best
8.	F8	No irritation	Pass

❖ **Table No. 16: Washability Test**

- Small amount of the prepared cream was applied evenly to a specific area of the skin and then exposed to running water for a certain period of time. After that, it was observed how easily the cream washed off from the skin surface.
- F7 batch showed excellent washability with a smooth feel after application. It was completely washable, non-greasy, and skin-friendly, indicating good formulation balance and better patient acceptability compared to other batches.

Sr. No	Formulation	Observation	Result
1.	F1	Difficult to wash	Poor
2.	F2	Easily washable	Good
3.	F3	Easily washable	Good
4.	F4	Easily washable	Good
5.	F5	Slightly oily	Poor
6.	F6	Easily washable	Very good
7.	F7	Completely washable with smooth feel	Excellent
8.	F8	Easily washable	Good

❖ **Table No. 17: Ph Determination**

- The ideal ph range for topical herbal cream is 5.5 to 6.5 solution of the cream was prepared by weighing 1 g of cream and dissolving it in 10 ml of water. Once the proper solution was prepared, the ph value was determined using ph paper.
- The ph study showed that f7 batch had a ph of 6.2, which was within the ideal skin-friendly range, (5.5–6.5). Hence, f7 was considered the best and most suitable formulation for topical application.

Sr. No	Formulations	Observation	Result
1.	F1	5.2 ph	Fail
2.	F2	5.4 ph	Fail
3.	F3	5.5 ph	Pass
4.	F4	6.8 ph	Fail
5.	F5	6.7 ph	Fail
6.	F6	5.3 ph	Fail
7.	F7	6.2 ph	Best
8.	F8	6.9 ph	Fail

❖ **Table No. 18: Viscosity**

- The viscosity of the formulated batches was determined using brookfield viscometer with spindle of 64 at 20 rpm. The formulation whose viscosity determined was added to the beaker the spindle was allowed to move freshly into crack cream and reading was noted.
- The viscosity study showed that formulations f5, f6, and f7 were within the ideal viscosity range (22000–24000 cp), indicating good consistency and suitability for topical application. Among all batches, f7 showed the best viscosity (23500 cp), providing optimum smoothness, stability, and easy application on cracked skin.

Sr. No	Formulations	Observation	Result
1.	F1	18500 cp	Fail
2.	F2	19800 cp	Fail
3.	F3	20500 cp	Fail
4.	F4	21400 cp	Fail
5.	F5	22100 cp	Pass
6.	F6	22800 cp	Pass
7.	F7	23500 cp	Best
8.	F8	24500 cp	Fail

❖ **Table no. 19: Spreadability**

- A small amount of cream is placed between two glass slides. A weight is applied, and the time taken for the upper slide to move is noted.

- The spreadability test showed that the formulated herbal crack cream could be applied easily on the skin surface. Formulation f7 exhibited excellent spreadability with a smooth feel and uniform application. Good spreadability helps the cream cover the affected area properly and improves absorption of herbal ingredients into the skin. It also enhances patient comfort and ease of use during application.

Sr.no.	Formulation	Observation	Result
1.	F1	Moderate spreading	Good
2.	F2	Easily spreadable	Good
3.	F3	Smooth spreading	Good
4.	F4	Excellent spreading	Excellent
5.	F5	Slightly greasy spreading	Good
6.	F6	Moderate spreading	Good
7.	F7	Easily spreadable with smooth feel	Excellent
8.	F8	Easily spreadable with Smooth feel	Good

❖ Table No. 20: Stability Test

- The ideal range for topical herbal crack cream at refrigerator temperature is $4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and at room temperature at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.
- The stability study indicated that the prepared herbal crack cream remained stable under both refrigerator and room temperature conditions. Formulation f7 showed the best stability without phase separation, change in texture, or loss of smoothness. Good stability ensures that the cream maintains its consistency, appearance, and effectiveness during storage and use.

Sr.no	Formulation	Refrigerator temperature ($4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$)	Room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$)	Result
1.	F1	Stable	Slightly soft	Pass
2.	F2	Stable	Stable	Good
3.	F3	Slightly stable	Phase separation Observed	Moderate
4.	F4	Highly stable	Highly stable	Excellent
5.	F5	Stable	Slightly oily	Good
6.	F6	Stable	Slightly thin Consistency	Moderate
7.	F7	Highly stable	Highly stable with Smooth texture	Best
8.	F8	Stable	Stable	Good

7. CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to formulate a herbal heel fissure cream enriched with coconut oil to

manage cracked heels effectively. The prepared cream showed several therapeutic benefits such as anti-inflammatory, pain-relieving, antifungal, antimicrobial, and antibacterial activities, which can support the healing process and reduce the risk of secondary skin infections.

Evaluation of different formulations revealed that formulation f7 produced the most satisfactory results in terms of stability, uniform texture, ease of application, and skin compatibility without causing irritation. As consumer demand for herbal and natural skincare products continues to rise, this cream has the potential to be a safe and effective substitute for synthetic heel care formulations.

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